

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

PROJECT	
Project acronym:	EVIDENTIAL
Project name:	rEVeallng Drug Effects when applyiNg psychomeTrics In schizophreniA triaLs
Grand Agreement No:	101209817
Duration:	12 months
Call identifier:	HORIZON-MSCA-2024-PF-01

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1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for?
<p>Yes. This project re-use individual participant data (IPD) from randomized controlled trials (RCTs) of antipsychotics in schizophrenia/schizoaffective/psychotic disorders.</p> <p>Re-used data will be used to (i) fit and compare state-of-the-art psychometric models of Positive and Negative Syndrome Scale (PANSS)/Brief Psychiatric Rating Scale (BPRS) (factor-analytic, item response theory, network approaches), and (ii) re-estimate and compare treatment effects using conventional sum scores versus psychometrically informed scores.</p> <p>We will not generate new primary clinical data.</p>
State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
<p>Re-use alternatives were considered but discarded include relying only on published aggregate results; this was discarded because item-level modelling and testing require IPD.</p>
What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
<p>Dataset</p> <p><i>Re-used (restricted):</i> Anonymised clinical trial IPD (tabular datasets; typically .CSV/.XLSX formats), including PANSS/BPRS item-level data, visit timing, treatment allocation, and baseline covariates where available.</p> <p><i>Generated (shareable):</i> Derived aggregate datasets: non-disclosive outputs intended for sharing: trial-level effect sizes, model-fit statistics, parameter estimates (e.g., loadings, thresholds), invariance/DIF summaries, codebooks, analysis logs.</p> <p>Documentation accompanying the data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Research software/code: R scripts, workflow files, Codebooks, documentation.• Figures/tables used for publications and reports.
What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Re-used IPD enables psychometric model comparison at the item level (objective 1: Determine the best psychometric models for the PANSS and BPRS).• Generated derived outputs enable objective 2: quantify whether treatment-effect estimates change when best-fitting/weighted psychometric scores are used instead of sum scores (including invariance analysis), and to support transparent, reproducible reporting.
What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
<p>Re-used IPD size is expected to be ~1–10 GB total (depending on number of trials, visits, and file formats). Derived shareable outputs and code are expected to be <5 GB.</p>

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

Re-used IPD: obtained from trial sponsors (Abbott, AbbVie, Janssen, Johnson & Johnson, Lilly, Otsuka) and established clinical trial data-sharing platforms (Vivli.org and <https://yoda.yale.edu/>) under Data Use Agreements (DUAs) and access approvals (e.g., sponsor portals/platforms).

Sponsor	Sponsor ID	Study ID	Primary DOI	Data Package DOI
Abbott	M02-547	NCT00073164	https://doi.org/10.25934/00002955	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00002955.0
AbbVie	RGH-MD-24	NCT03593213	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011273	-
Lilly ¹	2347	NCT00036088	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004367	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004367.0
Lilly ¹	8047	NCT00088049	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011613	-
Lilly ¹	5995	NCT00088465	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004381	-
Lilly ¹	5984	NCT00088478	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004382	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004382.0
Lilly ¹	5985	NCT00088491	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004383	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004383.0
Lilly ¹	8333	NCT00100776	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011611	-
Lilly ¹	5296	NCT00190749	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011612	-
Lilly ¹	6390	NCT00320489	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004406	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004406.0
Lilly ¹	13333	NCT00970281	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004467	-
Janssen ²	CR011992	NCT00378092	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004726	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004726.0
Janssen ³	CR003358	NCT00216580	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004641	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004641.0
Janssen ³	CR002257	NCT00216671	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004646	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004646.1
Janssen ³	CR003211	NCT00216632	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004645	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004645.0
Janssen ³	CR006061	NCT00249223	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004672	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004672.1
Janssen ³	CR002263	NCT00369239	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004725	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004725.0
Janssen ⁴	CR017026	NCT01299389	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004827	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004827.1
Janssen ⁴	CR017077	NCT01258920	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004819	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004819.0
Janssen ⁵	CR100662	NCT01515423	https://doi.org/10.25934/00005197	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00005197.1
Janssen ⁵	CR100427	NCT01662310	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004853	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004853.0
Janssen ⁵	CR108390	NCT03345342	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00008737	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00008737.0
Janssen ⁵	CR100717	NCT01529515	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004845	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004845.0
Janssen ⁵	CR016675	NCT01009047	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004788	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004788.1
Janssen ⁶	CR016618	NCT01193153	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004812	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004812.0
Janssen ⁷	CR002758	NCT00236379	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004651	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004651.0
Janssen ⁷	CR006055	NCT00253136	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004677	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004677.1
Janssen ⁷	CR006067	NCT00249132	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004669	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004669.0
Janssen ⁷	CR002017	NCT00495118	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004739	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004739.1
Janssen ⁸	CR013162	NCT00566631	https://doi.org/10.25934/00005196	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00005196.0
Janssen ⁸	CR012949	NCT00460512	https://doi.org/10.25934/00005195	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00005195.0
Janssen ⁸	CR017215	NCT01281527	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004820	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004820.0
Janssen ⁸	CR015199	NCT01081769	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004796	-
Janssen ⁸	CR013189	NCT00645099	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004753	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004753.0
Janssen ⁸	CR002269	NCT00216476	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004638	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004638.1
Janssen ⁹	CR108121	NCT02713282	https://doi.org/10.25934/00005198	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00005198.0
Janssen ¹³	CR013150	NCT00604279	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004751	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004751.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR010498	NCT00397033	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004729	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004729.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR013099	NCT00412373	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004730	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004730.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003274	NCT00236587	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004658	-
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004357	NCT00074477	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004595	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004595.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004198	NCT00111189	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004612	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004612.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003376	NCT00650793	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004756	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004756.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR010501	NCT00334126	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004722	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004722.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004381	NCT00085748	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004601	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004601.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004423	NCT00752427	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004768	-
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002944	NCT00668837	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00008735	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00008735.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003379	NCT00078039	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004598	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004598.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004375	NCT00083668	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004600	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004600.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003289	NCT00645307	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004755	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004755.0

Sponsor	Sponsor ID	Study ID	Primary DOI	Data Package DOI
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002350	NCT00119756	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004614	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004614.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004195	NCT00210717	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004628	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004628.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR012550	NCT00590577	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004750	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004750.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR012289	NCT00589914	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004749	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004749.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004384	NCT00086320	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004603	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004603.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR004378	NCT00077714	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004597	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004597.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002353	NCT00210548	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004625	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004625.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003562	NCT00101634	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004610	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004610.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002281	NCT00105326	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004611	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004611.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002761	NCT00034775	https://doi.org/10.25934/00005178	-
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002026	NCT00236457	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004654	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004654.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002899	NCT00297388	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004707	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004707.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR006121	NCT00299702	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004709	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004709.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR016687	NCT01050582	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004791	-
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003370	NCT00088075	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004604	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004604.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR003361	NCT00034749	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004583	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004583.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	CR002368	NCT00518323	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004740	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004740.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	RIS-INT-85	-	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004909	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004909.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	RIS-USA-72	-	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004901	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004901.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	RIS-USA-1 (RIS-USA-9001)	-	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004898	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004898.1
Johnson & Johnson ¹⁰	RIS-BEL-7	-	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011290	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011290.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹¹	CR016522	NCT01051531	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004792	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004792.0
Johnson & Johnson ¹¹	CR100739	NCT01527305	https://doi.org/10.25934/00004844	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00004844.0
Otsuka ¹²	31-07-246	NCT00705783	https://doi.org/10.25934/00006884	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00006884.0
Otsuka ¹²	31-07-247	NCT00706654	https://doi.org/10.25934/00006885	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00006885.0
Otsuka ¹²	31-12-291	NCT01663532	https://doi.org/10.25934/00006886	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00006886.0
Otsuka ¹²	331-10-237	NCT01397786	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011624	https://doi.org/10.25934/PR00011624.0

Note.¹ Eli Lilly and Company² Janssen Cilag N.V./S.A.³ Janssen Pharmaceutica N.V., Belgium⁴ Janssen Pharmaceutical K.K.⁵ Janssen Research & Development, LLC⁶ Janssen Scientific Affairs, LLC⁷ Janssen, LP⁸ Janssen-Cilag International NV⁹ Janssen-Cilag Ltd.¹⁰ Johnson & Johnson Pharmaceutical Research & Development, L.L.C.¹¹ Johnson & Johnson Pte Ltd¹² Otsuka Pharmaceutical Development & Commercialization, Inc.¹³ Xian-Janssen Pharmaceutical Ltd.

Generated outputs: produced via scripted processing pipelines (data harmonisation → psychometric modelling → effect estimation), with version control and full provenance recorded (see Sections 2.4 and 5).

<p>To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers in psychometrics, psychiatric outcomes, and meta-analysis • Clinical guideline developers and trialists designing endpoints for psychosis trials • Clinicians working on schizophrenia trial methodology. • Methodologists evaluating e.g. measurement invariance in clinical trials • Regulators/HTA bodies interested in robustness of symptom-scale endpoints • Statistical methodologists.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

<p>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p> <p>Yes. All shareable research outputs (code, documentation, derived aggregate datasets) will be deposited in a repository that assigns a persistent identifier (DOI) (e.g., OSF, Zenodo or equivalent).</p>
<p>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?</p> <p>Yes. We will provide rich metadata describing: title, authors, affiliations, funder/grant, abstract, keywords, methods summary, temporal coverage, variable summaries for derived datasets, and links to associated publications.</p> <p>We will use repository-supported standards such as DataCite metadata (via DOI registration).</p>
<p>What metadata standards will be followed?</p> <p>For trial-level derived datasets, we will include a consistent schema (variable names, units, coding, missingness flags) and trial identifiers as permitted by DUAs</p>
<p>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata?</p> <p>Yes, (e.g., “IPD meta-analysis”, “PANSS”, “BPRS”, “psychometrics”, “item response theory”, “measurement invariance”, “antipsychotics”, “schizophrenia”).</p>
<p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p> <p>Yes. Depositing in a repository such as Zenodo enables harvesting/indexing via standard mechanisms (e.g. OpenAIRE).</p>

2.2. Making data accessible

2.2.1. Repository

<p>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?</p> <p>Open outputs (planned): We will deposit code, documentation, and derived aggregate datasets in a trusted repository that assigns DOIs and resolves to a landing page (e.g., Zenodo, OSF + DOI).</p> <p>Restricted IPD: Raw IPD will not be deposited openly; access remains governed by the original data controllers/platforms and DUAs.</p>
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Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
Yes. Zenodo and OSF confirm suitability for archiving.
Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?
Yes. Each record receives a persistent DOI.

2.2.2. Data

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
<p>Not openly shareable: IPD from RCTs contains anonymised personal data and is subject to legal, ethical, and contractual restrictions (GDPR, consent limitations, DUAs, sponsor/platform terms).</p> <p>Openly shareable: Derived outputs that are non-disclosive (aggregate trial-level estimates, psychometric parameters where permitted, model fit indices) plus all analysis code, documentation, and synthetic/example data will be made openly available.</p>
If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
If needed, an embargo of (e.g., up to 6–12 months) may be applied to open outputs to allow publication; metadata will remain available immediately.
Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
Yes. For open outputs (HTTPS access via repository). Restricted IPD will be accessible via the relevant platform’s standard secure access procedures.
If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
<p>During: Access only to authorised project members under DUAs via secure environments.</p> <p>After: IPD access requests must be made to the original data providers/platforms. We will provide clear instructions and citations in the repository README describing how third parties can seek access and reproduce analyses if access is granted.</p>
How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
For restricted IPD: via platform identity verification, institutional email, signed agreements, and where applicable named-user accounts.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

For IPD, access decisions are handled by the data controllers/platform DACs. Internally, we will designate roles to ensure that only approved users have access consistent with DUAs.

2.2.3. Metadata

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Yes. Metadata for open deposits will be openly available and, where possible, dedicated under CC0. Metadata will clearly state restrictions for IPD and provide directions for requesting access from the relevant platforms, such as NCT identifier and links to these platforms

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Open outputs will be preserved for at least 10 years (or longer per repository policy). Metadata will remain available even if any files are removed/updated, with versioning and tombstone pages where applicable.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

Yes. We will include README, codebooks, and references to required software. Code will be open-source and, where feasible, containers to enable reproducibility.

2.3. Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

- Open, non-proprietary formats for shareable outputs: CSV, JSON (metadata), PDF (reports).
- Clear variable naming conventions and harmonised dictionaries for PANSS/BPRS items, visit timing, treatment arms, and baseline covariates.
- Where feasible, we will map key variables to commonly used conventions (e.g., standard coding for sex, visit weeks, trial arm labels). If original trial data are in CDISC-like structures (SDTM/ADaM), we will preserve mappings.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?
Yes. Any project-specific derived variables (e.g., latent scores, model IDs, invariance flags) will be documented and mapped to underlying items and timepoints in the codebook.
Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?
Yes. Derived datasets will include qualified references to trial identifiers (as permitted), model specifications (with versioned IDs), and links to associated code releases and publications (via DOI).

2.4. Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
<p>We will provide:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • README describing objectives, data inputs, and reproduction steps • A data dictionary/codebook for derived datasets • Workflow documentation (pipeline steps, parameter settings) • Session info / package versions; lockfiles; seeds • Analytic notebooks or scripted reports (e.g. R Markdown/Quarto) generating key tables/figures
Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
<p>Code: open-source license (e.g., CC BY 4.0)</p> <p>Derived aggregate datasets: license consistent with repository and funder requirements (e.g., CC BY 4.0), subject to DUA constraints</p> <p>Metadata: CC0 where possible</p>
Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
Yes, for open outputs; restricted IPD reuse depends on data controller permissions. Our open code and synthetic data will allow third parties to understand methods and reproduce results if they obtain lawful access to the same IPD.
Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
Yes, version-controlled pipelines (e.g., Git), changelogs, data processing logs, and structured provenance notes (e.g., input file checksums, timestamps, processing steps).

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

- Automated range checks and validation rules for PANSS/BPRS item ranges and totals
- Harmonisation checks (visit alignment, consistent coding)
- Missingness profiling (by item, visit, trial, arm)
- Reproducible audit trails (logs) for all transformations
- Double-checks of trial-level summary statistics against published reports where feasible

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

To increase re-use, we will provide comprehensive documentation enabling independent validation and replication, including files describing the workflow, data processing steps, and variable definitions; structured codebooks/data dictionaries for derived datasets; and fully annotated analysis scripts/notebooks.

In addition to research data, we will manage and share other research outputs, such as statistical code, model specifications (e.g., psychometric model definitions and parameter summaries where non-disclosive), analysis workflows, and the protocol, according to the same FAIR principles, using persistent identifiers and standard licences where appropriate.

Resource needs (curation time, storage, archiving, and compute) will be planned within the project and prioritised for materials that most directly enable reproducibility, while security and ethical requirements will be applied throughout: restricted IPD will remain in secure, access-controlled environments in line with GDPR and data use agreements, and only non-disclosive derived outputs and documentation will be released openly, with metadata clearly indicating access conditions and provenance.

3. Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Outputs beyond data include:

- Psychometric model specifications and parameter sets
- Analysis pipelines/workflows
- Protocol, and reporting templates
- Summary reports, visualisations, and dissemination materials (including patient/public-facing summaries if applicable)

These outputs will be managed with the same FAIR principles

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

These outputs will be included with the data that are shared in a public data repository such as Zenodo / OSF or Github

4. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?

Costs for making outputs FAIR (storage, archiving, security, etc.) will be kept to a minimum by depositing open outputs (e.g., code, documentation, and non-disclosive derived datasets) on free, trusted repositories that provide long-term preservation and persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI assignment).

How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)

Any remaining costs are expected to relate primarily to institutional secure storage and access-controlled computing for restricted IPD, as required by data use agreements and GDPR, and will be covered through existing institutional infrastructure and/or the project budget where applicable.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Data Management Lead: [Lead Applicant]

Technical Lead for pipelines/reproducibility: [Lead Applicant]

PI oversight and compliance: [PI]

How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

Open outputs: preserved in repository for ≥ 10 years.

Restricted IPD: stored only for the duration allowed by DUAs and institutional policy; long-term archiving decisions guided by DUA terms and institutional governance.

Decisions on retention/destruction will be made by [PI + institutional data protection/data governance].

5. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Restricted IPD will be stored on encrypted, access-controlled institutional infrastructure (e.g., secure server/HPC), with:

- Role-based access
- Encrypted storage and encrypted transfer (SFTP/HTTPS/VPN)
- Logging/auditing of access where feasible
- Regular backups and disaster recovery per institutional policy
- No storage on personal devices; no onward sharing outside approved environments

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Open outputs will be stored in trusted repositories with redundancy and preservation policies.

6. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).

Yes. IPD are anonymised personal/sensitive health data. Sharing is constrained by GDPR, ethics approvals/consent terms from original trials, and DUAs with data controllers. We will share only non-disclosive derived outputs and code openly.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No new consent will be collected because the project uses existing trial data. We will comply with the consent and governance framework applicable to each trial dataset and platform.

7. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

We will follow:

- Institutional Research Data Management policies of RCSI
- Funder requirements (Horizon Europe/Grant Agreement) regarding open science and metadata availability
- Platform-specific governance policies for each IPD source (data-sharing portal terms, publication review if required)